

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS AND NECESSITY OF FORMING INNOVATIVE THINKING IN YOUTH STUDENTS

Xalikova Latofat Uktamovna

Tashkent State transport University
Associate professor of the department "Foreign languages"

Students of the University of Transport

Saburov Zafarbek

Nusratullayev Afro'zbek

Bozorov Jamshid

Murodov Murod

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes in detail the methodological foundations and necessity of forming innovative thinking of students and youth, the impact of innovative thinking on economic, political and cultural changes in society, as well as the activities of young people in creative thinking and creating new ideas. Innovative thinking is important not only in creating technological innovations, but also in improving social systems, education and healthcare. The article examines the contribution of young people to the development of society through their active participation in startups, entrepreneurship and scientific research. Innovative thinking is a key tool in renewing and modernizing society by introducing young people to new knowledge and using their creative approaches.

Keywords: Globalization, youth, national idea, creative thought, awareness of national identity, thinking, innovation.

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada talaba-yoshlarning innovatsion tafakkurini shakllantirishning metodologik asoslari va zarurati hamda innovatsion tafakkurning jamiyatdagi iqtisodiy, siyosiy va madaniy o'zgarishlarga ta'siri, shuningdek, yoshlarning kreativ fikrlash va yangi g'oyalar yaratishdagi faoliyati batafsil tahlil qilinadi. Innovatsion tafakkur nafaqat texnologik yangiliklarni yaratishda, balki ijtimoiy tizimlarni yaxshilashda, ta'limda va

sog'liqni saqlashda ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada yoshlarning startaplar, tadbirkorlik va ilmiy tadqiqotlar sohalarida faol ishtirok etishlari orqali jamiyatni rivojlantirishga qo'shgan hissalarini ko'rib chiqiladi. Innovatsion tafakkur yoshlarni yangi bilimlar bilan tanishtirish va ularning kreativ yondashuvlarini qo'llash orqali jamiyatni yangilash va modernizatsiya qilishda asosiy vosita sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Globallashuv, yoshlar, milliy g'oya, kreativ fikr, milliy o'zlikni anglash, tafakkur, innovatsiya.

The "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, provides for the complete revision and implementation of curricula and textbooks by 2026 based on advanced foreign experience, increasing the coverage of higher education to 50 percent and improving the quality of education, granting academic and financial independence to state higher educational institutions, including establishing the practice of independently determining their remuneration, number of employees, amount of payment contracts and form of education, clearly defining the relevant rights and powers of state higher educational institutions, targeted preparation of 10 potential higher educational institutions for entry into the QS and TNE international rankings by 2026, development of a targeted program for higher educational institutions to enter the QS and TNE international rankings, Based on its potential and specific characteristics, it has been determined to implement tasks such as developing and approving targeted programs for 5 years for inclusion in international ratings. Just as human development cannot be imagined without thought, the history of society cannot be explained without ideas and ideologies. In particular, the national idea, which has served as the main factor in the rise of various societies and peoples in the historical development of mankind, is not a phenomenon that appears in a short period of time. In fact, even an idea that seems to have appeared suddenly has centuries-old development of consciousness. Viewed from this perspective, the national idea is the product of long processes and embodies the history, worldview, goals and aspirations, and spirituality of the people.

The national idea is a product of a long-standing national way of thinking and a continuous process that is being improved by the demands of the times. In this context, it is appropriate to answer the questions "What is the national idea?", "What is its political, philosophical, legal and spiritual essence?". In our opinion, the national idea is

the fundamental content of the ideology of independence, a beacon that calls and mobilizes the country to great goals. The national idea cannot be invented. It is a law that every era and every people have their own ideas of perfection. From this point of view, the national idea is the spiritual and moral basis of the nation's improvement, its striving for perfection, the main goal, the tactical path and strategy.

According to journalist and political scientist N. Joraev, "The national idea is formed on the basis of national consciousness and traditions, lifestyle, and only an idea consciously united by the light of reason around the national interest, elevated to the level of universal human value, becomes a national ideology." Indeed, any society is built on the basis of a national idea and ideology.

Academician E. Yusupov, emphasizing that ideas and ideology are formed in connection with human society and its needs in general, expresses the following opinion: "The national idea is a spiritual factor that unites blood-related, soul-mate people with the same ethnic roots, history, language, culture, homeland, faith, spirituality, economic life, values, traditions and customs towards certain goals and interests, and coordinates and directs their activities." The scientist sees ideology as a decisive factor in the development of society, as a means of bringing clarity and clarity to ideas that direct a person's conscious activity towards a specific goal, and as a means of mobilizing the masses.

In socio-philosophical sources, the concept of "national idea" is approached differently and various definitions and descriptions are given. The opinion of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the concept of "national idea" sheds more light on its content: "When we say national idea, we mean something that has been passed down from ancestors to generations, has been cherished for centuries, has taken deep roots in the hearts of every person and the entire nation living in this country, has become its spiritual need and life requirement, if we can say so, if we imagine the most noble dreams, aspirations, hopes and goals of any nation, I think we will express the essence of such a broad concept."

Summarizing the opinions expressed by researchers, we propose to define the concept of "national idea" as follows: a national idea is a set of strong, deep thoughts and views that embody the past, present and future of a particular nation in its thinking, have a strong influence on the psyche of society and people, call it to action, and lead it towards a goal.

Not every idea can be a national idea. Personal thoughts and views can grow and turn into social thought. Social thought, on the other hand, expresses an active attitude towards reality that requires change or purposeful action.

The national idea and ideology are social values, and their methodological foundations are the supreme goal, noble intention of each historical period and historical figure - the leader, the main program of state development. Therefore, the harmony of ideas and ideologies with historical progress is an important condition for the development of humanity. At the same time, any idea and ideology can become a real reality only on the basis of the interests of the people and the nation. Only an idea that embodies the national interest will be viable and has the potential to become a material force. For example, the main ideas of the national ideology have now been formed. They have been tested throughout the historical development of our people. The following can be cited as the basic ideas of our national ideology:

- a single sense of homeland;
- justice - the rule of law;
- popular consent;
- enlightenment against ignorance;
- innovative development.

Today, a whole system of national ideas and ideology has been developed in our country. The more majestic and reliable it is, the more conscious self-sacrifice, deep intellectual and emotional responsibility and perfection, political, legal and religious culture it requires from society.

In this sense, in our opinion, the ideology of national revival has come into being as a new consciousness and worldview for independence. National ideology is a tactic, and historically it is manifested in political, moral, legal, religious, aesthetic and philosophical forms.

The main idea of the national ideology is a set of dreams, hopes, and the most progressive thoughts aimed at the strategic goal "From national revival to national elevation", determining its development.

A person with a high level of spirituality does not act contrary to the interests of his people. But in order for everyone to reach a level that meets such great spiritual criteria, there must be a way of thinking nourished by a strong national ideology. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, said: "Since we

have decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we will rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values.” Indeed, the Uzbek people are proud of their great past, and they deserve to be proud.

Considering the fact that the essence of a person is in the mind, and the essence of the mind is manifested in character, it becomes clear that the only criterion reflecting a person's humanity is the level of intelligence and thinking, and the main criterion that reveals their content and assesses their scale is their behavior, attitude to life and the environment, and their inner strength to control themselves. Relying on this inner strength, our people have been honoring the further development of such qualities and traits as religion, prayer, and thought as the highest value. It is not difficult to understand how important it is to instill these in the minds and hearts of young people through spirituality and the national idea.

When the national idea and ideology reflect the demands of humanity and the aspirations of the people, they become an incomparable factor in uniting members of society and fully revealing its potential. At this point, it is appropriate to recall the metaphorical thought that “It is not enough to hear the national idea with the ears, it is necessary to feel and understand it with the heart.” It is such that as a person grows up, his belief in the historically formed national culture, lifestyle, traditions and customs becomes stronger. Therefore, the national idea should also be considered as a spiritual foundation that has been formed and developed in the process of long historical development and ensures the stability and integrity of a certain unity. This spiritual foundation is manifested in the hearts of representatives of the nation in the form of patriotism, nationalism, a sense of national pride, historical memory, an awareness of national identity, a sense of duty and responsibility. Language, morality, and the national spirit that ensure national unity also affect the strengthening of the national idea. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, emphasized: “The ideology of the new Uzbekistan we are creating will be the idea of goodness, humanity, humanism. By ideology, we mean, first of all, the education of thought, the education of national and universal values. They are based on the vital concepts and values of our people, which are thousands of years old.” Indeed, the national idea and ideology must always be in motion, in a certain sense, be updated, and regularly enriched under the influence of other values. Otherwise, it will be no different from

fanaticism. No matter how much the tasks and conditions facing society change, its basic principles remain constant - they will not change. This is the uniqueness of society, the condition of its existence, the binding force. Any society based on mass information will have immutable beliefs inherited from the existing society, and they will serve as the foundation for development. Therefore, it is the responsibility of intellectuals and scientists to promote them.

The laws of social development are reflected in the laws of national development (the first is general, the second is specific). The laws of national development constitute the theoretical and methodological foundations of the country's independent development. (This can be clearly observed in the philosophical content of the "Uzbek model"). The study of such problems is the object of philosophy. The national idea and ideology are formed and develop on the basis of philosophical knowledge about them. Only if the national idea is philosophically based, it will be possible to systematize work in this area, thus clearly describing the fundamental interests and goals of each person, group, category in society, and the ways to realize them. Accordingly, without philosophy, it is impossible to effectively solve the problem of both the theoretical and practical aspects of the idea and ideology. It is impossible to separate the idea and ideology from philosophy (or rather, from its philosophical basis). An idea and ideology that does not have its own philosophical foundations or is separated from it may not be of significant importance in social life, and may even have a negative impact on the development of a person and society. For example, today, many extremists and fanatics separate the noble ideas of our holy religion from the original Islamic philosophy, distort the fundamental content and essence of this religion, and subjectivize their interpretations, so their ideas and ideologies contradict the laws of the development of current social life, negatively affecting both the development of the Islamic religion and the development of humanity. Therefore, it is necessary to fully understand the reactionary nature of such fanatical, extremist and terrorist ideology and to study Islamic philosophy in depth in the fight against it.

In this regard, the same can be said about the actions of those who are trying to teach us democracy from the outside and introduce it in a systematic way. That is, first of all, their ideas and concepts about democracy do not correspond to the conditions here - the laws of social development.

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